

Metaphors of War, Ontology, and Journeys in the Inaugural Speeches of Good luck Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu

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Abstract:

This study examines the metaphors of war, ontology, and journeys in the inaugural speeches of Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu, former presidents of Nigeria. The study is necessitated by the need to establish the fact that Nigerian presidents use metaphors to communicate their political views, ideologies and goals to the public in a relatable way. The main data of qualitative research are the two inaugural addresses of former Nigerian presidents, Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu. Drawing upon Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT), and Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA), the research explores how these political leaders employed metaphors to construct narratives of governance, identity, and national destiny. The result, therefore, reveals that there are ontological, war, journey metaphors. From the identified conceptual metaphor, 21 metaphorical themes were discerned. Juxtaposing the two presidents' density of metaphorical usage, Jonathan and Tinubu focused on ontological metaphor as they assert political issues to an 'entity' and 'machine' that should be handled physically. Moreover, Tinubu and Jonathan used journey metaphor as they wanted to paint a picture portraying the political process as a confluence of movement towards a goal. Again, they used war metaphor as they were interested in fighting and tackling corruption. The study contribute to our understanding of metaphorical discourse in political communication and its implications for shaping public perceptions and policies in diverse cultural and political settings. Based on this, this study recommends that political leaders use metaphors to simplify complex political view, influence political participation and in the long run achieve their social goals.

Keywords: Language, Conceptual Metaphor, Political Discourse, Inaugural Speeches

Introduction

Language is a vital part of a man's life and an indispensable resource necessary for his day to day activities. It is a tool for expressing man's social reality as it performs various functions ranging from phatic communication to assertive, declarative, commissive and referential functions. Language makes us human; it is inseparable from the user (society). It does not exist in a vacuum but lives in the lips of the speaker. Leech (1981: 40) concurs to this by saying that "in addition to having an informal purpose which everyone assumes that it is the most important, language has expressive characteristics which can be used to express the speaker's thought and feeling."

Politics is inevitably connected to power: to make decisions, control resources, people's behaviour as well as their values and one of the basic instruments with which political actors express power is through the use of language. Also, politics involves a struggle for power with the aim of putting political ideas into practice. Therefore, Politics is one of the spheres of social life in which language plays a significant role (Taiwo, 2013).

Political discourse, like declaration of candidacy for a political office, political campaigns and rallies, presentation of party manifestos, presidential inaugural addresses and other forms of political speeches is aimed at marketing the ideology of the candidates and the political parties they represent. The masses, on the other hand, create impressions based on politicians' physical presentation and style and most importantly persuasive language (Lenard and Covic, 2017).

When political discourse is delivered, the speaker hopes that his listeners understand the language conveyed. Beard (2000:35) observes that "making effective speech is a vital part of the politicians' roles in announcing policies and persuading the public." But the problem is that political discourse in general is abstract, wordy, tortuous and composed of complicated ideas. These may cause misunderstanding, pose difficulties for most people to understand and in the long run cannot achieve any positive effect. On the contrary, people need to understand the information being conveyed in a clear, concise and succinct way (Xu, 2010). If the political leaders use professional expressions to describe these abstract ideas; the audience will feel puzzled and may lose interest.

A successful political discourse, therefore, needs an explanatory device which gets the complex and abstract ideas absorbed into the people's way of thinking. One of the greatest strategies appeared to be adopted widely and also used effectively is metaphor.

Inaugural addresses are one of the most important and vivid representations of political speeches made by the presidents. Inaugural addresses occur when a new political leader has been elected to mark the commencement of a four-year term in a presidential system of government. Nigerian Presidential inaugurals are courageous, inspiring and claiming the promises of better days ahead. Moreover, the inaugurals are designed not just to state the president's political visions and mission, but also "to win as much support as possible from his audience" (Wilson, 2001:6). To achieve this effectiveness of persuasion, Nigerian presidential inaugural addresses take the advantage of metaphor to arouse the feelings of their audience, attract their attention, motivate them and boost their morale. Thus, an understanding of the metaphor used by Nigerian presidents in their inaugurals would expose the ideologies of these presidents in Nigerian political discourse. This paper therefore seeks to analyse the metaphors of war, ontology and journeys in the inaugural speeches of two Post-Military Nigerian Presidents: Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu.

Statement of the Problem

Inauguration day is of great significance to the new president because this is a very special moment when he faces the whole nation to express his fundamental political policies and principles for the country's development in the following four years. By implication, the inaugural address is meant to promote and make leadership acceptable to the people. On the part of the citizens, it is also aimed at increasing political participation. Consequently, to achieve these goals, the president will carefully weigh his words in his speech and polish them using metaphor which is an effective rhetorical strategy. This study, therefore, aims to

investigate metaphors of War, Ontology and Journey in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

- i. To identify the metaphors of war, ontology and Journey in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu.
- ii. To examine the functions of the prevailing metaphorical themes associated with the underlying conceptual metaphors in each president's inaugural address.
- iii. To juxtapose the usage of the metaphors of war, ontology and journey by Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu.
- iv. To analyse the ideological motivation and manipulative strategy behind Jonathan and Tinubu's use of the metaphors of war, ontology and Journey.

Research Questions

This study is aimed at analyzing metaphors of war, ontology and journey in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i. What is the evidence that the metaphors of War, Ontology and Journey are used in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu?
- ii. What are the functions of the prevailing metaphorical themes derived from the metaphors of war, ontology and journey used in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu?
- iii. What are the similarities and differences in their use of war, ontology and journey metaphors?
- iv. To what extent do Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu transmit their ideologies through their manipulative use of war, ontology and journey metaphors?

Literature Review

What is Metaphor?

Metaphor has been a central object of linguistic enquiry which has bothered scholars since ancient times.

Being studied from several different perspectives, a wide variety of disciplines including linguistics, philosophy, literary studies, psychology and education among others, have attempted to define, describe and analyse metaphors. Aristotle discussed metaphor in his work '*Poetics*' as well as '*Art of Rhetoric*'. Aristotle generally defines metaphor as 'transference of a name belonging elsewhere'(Aristotle, 2018).

Approaches of Metaphor:

The traditional approach: It regards metaphor as 'the exclusive domain of literary scholars and the odd linguists who were interested in rhetoric or stylistics" (Ungerer and Schmid, 1996:114). In addition, according to Lakoff and Johnson (1980:3) and Kovecses, (2002:vii), metaphor is viewed as an "ornamental device that is restricted to poetry and literature".

The cognitive approach: According to Lakoff and Johnson (1980:3), metaphor is not just a way of expressing ideas by means of language, but a way of thinking about things.” Metaphor is therefore considered as a systematic interrelation of multiple experiences which map one relatively stable domain to another. The relationship between the domains is described as a set of systematic correspondences which are often referred to as mappings (Kovecses 2002).

Functions of Metaphors

Pedagogy: Metaphor can be a tool in teaching that supports decoding the unfamiliar with the capacity to transfer learning and understanding from what is known to what is less well-known and to do so in a very vivid manner (Ortony 1975).

Framing Device: Metaphors can have a profound effect on the ways people understand and reason about important issues as diverse as behavioural science, economics, technology, health and safety legislation, by creating a particular frame of reference (Hartman, 2012; Preacher and Hayes, 2008)

Social communication: metaphor leads to a kind of an intimate atmosphere between speakers. This creates a link based on the same or, at least, similar experiences and interests (Gibbs, 1993). Cohen (1978) goes further to suggest that the use of metaphorical language can also be a means of ‘cultivating intimacy’.

Political Discourse

Wilson (2001: 398) describes political discourse as “a language used in formal and informal political contexts with political media and political supporters operating in political environments with political goals.” Politics is one of the realities in our social world. Since language is the creator of the social world, it is therefore inevitable that, the concept of language and political discourse are interwoven and intrinsically linked (Ademilokun, 2018). Moreover, politics is basically about struggling to control power, language is used to accomplish the control of power, thereby making language a very strong political weapon. Since politics is basically about struggling to control power, language is used to accomplish the control of power, thereby making language a very strong political weapon. Language is used to instruct, inform, motivate, persuade, entertain and influence the citizenry.

Metaphor in Political Discourse

Among other rhetorical devices used in political discourse, metaphor is one of the most important among these devices because at the core of political communication is the ability of politicians to use metaphors that awaken the latent tendencies among the masses (Mio, 1996). Metaphor is, in fact, inseparable from political discourse and understanding. Johansen (2007:16) confirms this by stating that:

when we, in addition, know that many of the concepts that are central to politics, concepts like democracy, freedom, rights, justice, taxes, education, elections, laws, economy, nations and war, are abstract, it indeed seems likely that political language will be, to speak figuratively, packed with metaphors.

Mio (1996:117) manifests how metaphors are effective device and tools in political discourse. He stated further that:

Metaphors in political discourse make complex issues comprehensible as they allow the audience to comprehend and understand the meaning of speeches delivered by the politicians. Also, metaphors are extolled by many political theorists as effective persuasive tool or have demonized metaphors as the politicians' manipulative devices.

Metaphors in Presidential Inaugural Speeches

Presidential inaugural speeches are delivered in the public place at a special moment. According to Xu (2010:5), "most presidential inaugural speeches are courageous, inspiring and claiming the promises of a brighter future, even though some of them are addressed in the darkest days. The presidential inaugurals are designed not only to state the president's political vision and mission, but also to win as much support as possible from his audience for the president (Wilson, 2001). In order to achieve this effectiveness of persuasion, many presidential inaugurals take advantage of 'emotional appeals' to arouse the feelings of his audience as to attract their attention to listen to what he is talking about, to boost their morale and to motivate them (Xu, 2010). In addition, the president will also employ a variety of rhetoric to create an emotional impact and to attain the goal of persuading people to support him. Thus, among other rhetoric employed in political speeches, "metaphors appear to be used more widely and serve the purpose more effectively, which to a great extent enhance the force and vividness of the language"

Theoretical Framework

In order to analyse the language of metaphor in the inaugural addresses of Nigerian post-military presidents, the researcher will adopt insights provided by: Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) anchored by a group of scholars in the 1990, Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) developed by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson and Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA) proposed by Jonathan Charteris-Black as the theoretical framework of the study.

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a cross-discipline set forth in the early 1990s by a group of scholars such as: Ruth Wodak (Vienna), Theo Van Leeuwen and Gunther Kress (London), Teun van Dijk (Amsterdam), Norman Fairclough (Lancaster) and others. CDA is an interdisciplinary approach that focuses particularly on the relationship between language and power. CDA basically analyses the use of language governed by ideological inclinations (Ezeifeka, 2013) and deconstructing hidden agenda represented in texts and discourse in order to separate ideologies from official meaning of linguistic items (Wodak, 2001). In the political context, CDA is aimed at demystifying the texts and speeches of those in possession of power (Fairclough, 2005).

Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) also known as 'Cognitive Metaphor Theory' was developed by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson. Lakoff and Johnson's introduction of the Conceptual Metaphor Theory changed the perception of metaphor by arguing that most of our ordinary conceptual system is metaphorical in nature and that metaphors are an integral and even a central part of language, instead of its peripheral element. The purpose of the CMT was to demonstrate that metaphor is pervasive in thought and action opposing the comparison theory that believe that the basis of metaphor is pre-existing similarities between the source and target domains. (Guo, 2013).

Conceptual metaphor is based on systematic correspondences (mapping) of elements from concrete ‘source’ domain onto element of a more abstract ‘target’ domain. This mapping enables people to use the information about the source as a framework for understanding corresponding aspects of the target (Stamenkovic, 2017). The conceptual domain from which we draw metaphorical expressions to understand another conceptual domain is called **source domain**, while the conceptual domain that is metaphorically understood this way is the **target domain**. (Kovecses, 2002). The source domain is a concrete domain while the target domain is an abstract one. According to Eziefeka (2018), cross-domain mapping can be understood given the formula **X IS Y**: where **X** represents the target domain and **Y** the source domain.

Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA) was propounded by Jonathan Charteris-Black in his book ‘Corpus Approaches to Critical Metaphor Analysis’ in 2004. Critical metaphor analysis is a meaningful enrichment to both Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT). This approach provides new insights to both CDA and CMT by integrating CDA, corpus linguistics, pragmatics and cognitive linguistics. Moreover, CMA is also referred to as “purposeful metaphor” because it is well known that the main function of metaphor in the context of public speeches is to, gain the attention of the audience, influence the audience opinion and establish trust (Charteris-Black, 2004)

Empirical Studies

Since Lakoff and Johnson’s declaration that metaphor is crucial to human cognition, many empirical studies from various areas of human experiences, among which is politics, prove the vitality of metaphor to the conceptual nature of the human mind. Several studies on political discourse have been based on the view that metaphor plays a central role in political discourse. These studies have argued that metaphors have significant rhetorical and persuasive uses in political discourse

Berg (2014) investigated the metaphorical language used in the inaugural addresses of four prominent American presidents. Using the Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT), Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA) and Framing as theoretical frameworks, the study analysed the inaugural speeches of George Bush, Barack Obama, Ronald Reagan and Bill Clinton as they portrayed their worldviews using metaphors. Based on their political affiliation, the study found out that American Democratic and Republican Presidents use different and shared metaphors to represent their worldviews. While the American Republican Presidents used conceptual metaphors depicting strength and masculinity, the American Democratic Presidents’ metaphorical language suggests their worldview of American exceptionalism reflecting femininity.

Similarly, Vestermark (2007) carried out a research on the personification of America in the first inaugural addresses of Ronald Reagan (1981), George H. W. Bush (1989), Bill Clinton (1993) and George

W. Bush (2001). The study focused on how these American presidents used metaphors in their inaugural addresses, how the metaphors used could be interpreted and what messages these metaphors sent to the receivers. The findings discovered that the conceptual metaphors used in the inaugural addresses of these American presidents were highly intentional, but not always as easy to detect. The study also revealed that in these American presidents’ inaugural

addresses, America was conceptualised as a HUMAN.

Xu (2010) applied the Conceptual Metaphor Theory proposed by Lakoff and Johnson to analyse political metaphors in the inaugural addresses of 6 renowned presidents in American history: Richard Nixon, Ronald Reagan, George Bush, Bill Clinton, George W. bush and Barrack Obama. The findings of the study found out that three common metaphors appeared in these American presidents' inaugural speeches. They are Journey Metaphors, Human Metaphors and War Metaphors.

Johansen (2007) examined political discourse of the British Isles' Conservative and Labour parties. The findings revealed that both parties used the STATE AS A PERSON metaphor to conceptualise Britain.

Sharifi; Firoozian, Ailin and Firoozian, Aida (2012) explored how the body parts played roles in Persian political texts as metaphorical expressions. The study was carried out on Persian newspapers published in Iran. The findings revealed that there were fifteen body members by which political metaphors were conceptualized and reflected in Persian political discourse. The result further revealed that among the human body parts which were conceptualised in Persian political text, the HEAD was the most frequent one.

Malan (2008) offers an analysis of the metaphors underlying contemporary South African political thoughts covering the period between 1994-2001. Majority of the metaphors investigated are shared by the five South African prominent politicians. The result concluded that the presidents view racism as something negative which needed to be resolved and reconciliation is seen as something worth maintaining or striving for.

Taiwo (2013) studied metaphors in Nigerian political discourse. His study blended the method of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) with that of Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) originated by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson in 1980 to discuss metaphoric expressions found in the data. Based on the findings of his study, the NATION was conceptualised as a FAMILY and as a PERSON. He further identifies the conceptual mappings of POLITICS AS A BATTLE, POLITICS AS A JOURNEY, POLITICS AS A GAME and POLITICIANS AS BUILDERS.

Research Methodology

The corpus of this study consisted of two inaugural speeches of two post-military Nigerian presidents: Goodluck Ebele Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu. The inaugural addresses were the data for this study. They were downloaded from the internet via www.guardiannewsngr.com. The study adopted the qualitative research design, otherwise known as the interpretive approach to research. This approach, therefore, enabled the identification, interpretation and analysis of the metaphors in the inaugural addresses. In order to achieve this, the analytical procedures of CDA, CMT and CMA were applied since it approached the discovered metaphors at a descriptive and interpretative level.

Findings

Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Tinubu used the object, war and journey metaphors in their inaugural addresses. From the identified conceptual metaphors, 40 metaphorical themes were discerned. The ontological metaphor has 21 metaphorical themes, war metaphor has 10 metaphorical and journey metaphor has 13 metaphorical themes

Figure 1. The total object, war and journey metaphors in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Tinubu

Journey Metaphor

The notion of politics is usually conceptualised in terms of a journey (Lakoff and Johnson, 1980; Kovecses, 2002). The most frequently encountered metaphorical expressions in the inaugural addresses of Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Ahmed Tinubu were those making up the conceptual metaphor POLITICS IS A JOURNEY and It is manifested by 11 expressions. The conceptual metaphor, POLITICS IS A JOURNEY, gave rise to the following conceptual correspondences or metaphorical themes

- i. NIGERIANS ARE TRAVELLERS
- ii. POLITICAL GOALS ARE DESTINATIONS
- iii. POLITICAL CHALLENGES/PROBLEMS ARE BUMPS
- iv. POLITICAL STRATEGIES ARE MAPS/ROUTES/PATHS

Nigerians are Travelers

This conceptual metaphor personified Nigerians as travellers who journey together to achieve a common goal. The post-military Nigerian presidents used this metaphor to call on Nigerians

to participate actively and collectively in journeying towards development.

- “Join me now as *we begin the journey of transforming Nigeria*” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “... may I offer a few comments regarding the election *that brought us to this juncture*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023).
- “*This nation’s journey* has been shaped by the prayers of millions, and the collective sacrifices of us all.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- “*Let us take the next great step in the journey they began* and believed in.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Political goals are destinations

Every journey has its destination, in the same vein, every leader has political objectives and goals he wants to achieve in governance. In the data under study, the political ‘destination’ the president bore in mind was: ‘unity’, ‘peace’, ‘prosperity’, ‘integrity’, economic strength’ ‘democracy’. This metaphor also presupposed that the Nigerian nation is still on the journey to greatness and is yet to obtain its chief objective of being ‘a developed nation’ with social, economic and political achievements.

- “As a nation, we have long ago *decided to march beyond the dimness of night into the open day of renewed national hope.*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023).
- “On this day, Nigeria affirms *its rightful place among the world’s great democracies.*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023).

Political challenges/problems are bumps

In order to subscribe to the emotion of the citizen, this metaphor was used as Nigerians are intimated with the fact that along the journey to a united and democratic nation, they would be faced with challenges. Nevertheless with enduring spirits they would be able to get through ‘the bumps’. Moreover, this was an effective way of informing the citizens that they should not expect immediate results from their administration because challenges are inevitable in achieving political goal.

- “*Yet here we are. We have stumbled at times,* but our resilience and diversity have kept us” going (Bola Tinubu, 2023).

Political strategies are maps/paths

Different political strategies to attain the desired height in political accomplishments were referred to as ‘paths/maps’. This metaphor gave insights and a sense of direction to the political strategies that would be executed. This metaphor was also adopted to heighten the citizens’ optimistic attitude towards the leaderships’ quest in restoring development to a military-torn country.

- “We are ready to *take off on the path* of sustained growth and economic development.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “ ...our founding fathers gave bravely of themselves *to place Nigeria on the map as an independent nation.*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Summary of Prevailing Metaphorical Themes in Journey Metaphors Used by Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Tinubu in their Inaugural Addresses.

Metaphorical Themes	Goodluck Jonathan(2011)	Bola Tinubu (2023)	Total
NIGERIANS ARE TRAVELLERS	1	3	4
POLITICAL GOALS ARE DESTINATIONS	0	2	2
POLITICAL CHALLENGES/ PROBLEMS ARE BUMPS	0	1	1
POLITICAL STRATEGIES ARE MAPS /PATHS	1	1	2
	2	7	9

War Metaphor

The conceptual metaphor, POLITICS IS WAR is frequently used in political language. Politics and political activities are perceived as war. War metaphors were employed by the presidents in their inaugural addresses to deliver a more combative discourse and to highlight the importance of high competence, moral strength, personal sacrifice and physical struggle in achieving social goals and political success. In the inaugural addresses of the post-military Nigerian presidents under review, the following war metaphors were identified:

- i. THE PRESIDENT IS A WAR COMMANDER AND FIGHTER
- ii. NIGERIANS ARE FIGHTERS AND DEFENDERS
- iii. SOCIAL EVILS ARE ENEMIES
- iv. ELECTION IS WAR

The president is a war commander/fighter

The function of this metaphorical theme is emotive, because the president represented himself as the commander in chief who is laddened with the responsibility of leading ‘Nigerian’ army through the war, which in this case implied different societal problems and social vices.

- *“I will continue to fight*, for your future, because I am one of you. I will continue to fight, for improved medical care for all our citizens. *I will continue to fight* for all citizens to have access to first class education. *I will continue to fight* for electricity to be available to all our citizens. *I will continue to fight* for an efficient and affordable public transport system for all our people. *I will continue to fight* for jobs to be created through productive partnerships.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)

Nigerians are fighters and defenders

This war metaphor presented in post-military Nigerian presidential inaugurals showed that Nigerians are defenders and fighters. First of all, when the Nigerian people were regarded as defend, they were called upon to defend some social goals that were of great importance. In this case, they referred to ‘*freedom*’, ‘*security*’, ‘*good leadership*’, ‘*democracy*’ and ‘*integrity*’.

- “***The fight against corruption is a war in which we must all enlist***, so that the limited resources of this nation will be used for the growth of our commonwealth.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “We ***fought for*** decolonization. We will now ***fight for*** democratization.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “***We shall defend the nation from terror*** and all forms of criminality that threaten the peace and stability of our country and our subregion.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- “As we ***contain threats to peace***, we shall ... lead the regional and ***continental quest for collective prosperity***.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Social evils are enemies

Obviously, there will be enemies in a war. For the Nigerian people, social evils and any other forces which hinder the progress of Nigeria were enemies. The social evils are: ‘*corruption*’, ‘*crime*’, ‘*poverty*’, ‘*disease*’, ‘*underdevelopment*’, ‘*insecurity*’, ‘*power shortage*’, ‘*terrorism*’, and ‘*unemployment*’. By conceptually presenting these social evils as enemies, the presidents aimed at telling the citizens that these social evils were capable to ruining the Nigerian nation if ignored.

- “Africa must develop its vast resources ***to tackle poverty and under-development***.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “... because neither prosperity nor justice can prevail ***amidst insecurity and violence... to effectively tackle this menace***, ...” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- “As we ***contain threats to peace***, we shall ... lead the regional and ***continental quest for collective prosperity***.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Election is war

Election was being metaphorized as war because it is a significant moment when different political aspirants ‘fight’ for different political positions. On the other hand, the ‘heart/support’ of the electorates was the ‘battleground’ where intensive and fierce political campaigns were targeted. Therefore, when declared winners, they believed they had ‘won a war’.

- “Let me at this point congratulate ***the elected Governors, Senators, members of the House of Representatives and those of the States Houses of Assembly for their victories at the polls***.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “However, ***my victory does not render me any more Nigerian than my opponents***.” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Summary of Prevailing Metaphorical Themes in War Metaphors Used by Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Tinubu in their Inaugural Addresses.

Metaphorical Themes	Goodluck Jonathan (2011)	Bola Tinubu (2023)	Total
THE PRESIDENT IS A WAR COMMANDER/ FIGHTER	1	0	1
NIGERIANS ARE FIGHTERS AND DEFENDERS	2	2	4
SOCIAL EVILS ARE ENEMIES	1	2	3
ELECTION IS WAR	1	1	2
TOTAL	5	5	10

Ontological/Object Metaphor

According to Ezeifeke (2018:198), ontological metaphor, also referred to as object metaphor involves “the projection of entity or substances status upon something that does not have the status inherently.” In other words, ontological metaphor “allows us to view events, activities, emotions, ideas as entities in order to categorize, group or quantify them.”

In the inaugural addresses of post-military Nigerian presidents, the concept of politics which is abstract is identified as a concrete entity and substance as it is metaphorically conceptualized as the following (physical metaphors):

- i. POLITICS IS A MACHINE
- ii. POLITICS IS BUSINESS
- iii. POLITICS IS A FORCE
- iv. POLITICS IS A CONTAINER
- v. POLITICS IS AN ENTITY

Politics is a machine

The machine metaphor was mostly used to represent politics as a ‘system’. The political leaders presented the following concepts of politics: ‘*peace and stability*’, ‘*democracy*’, ‘*infrastructure*’, ‘*the nation*’, ‘*the economy*’, as being a machine that can be ‘*fixed*’, ‘*mended*’, or ‘*broken*’. *Examples:*

- “The pivotal task of this generation is to *lift our fatherland* to the summit of greatness.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “We are *here to further mend ...*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- “Nigeria’s critics have trafficked the rumour that *our nation will break apart ...*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- “Our burdens *may make us bend* at times, but *they shall never break us...*” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Politics is food

Food metaphor was used to establish some phenomena in politics that are as essential as eating for growth, development and survival. In the inaugural addresses under study, ‘*democracy*’ is considered as ‘food’ that is desired by the nation. In other words, for the growth and development of Nigeria, democracy and national resources should be present. Example:

- “At the polls, we saw the most dramatic expressions of the *hunger for democracy*.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)

Politics is business

The money metaphor was noted in the corpus under study as it presents politics in terms of a business venture. Since every business is aimed at maximizing profit, ‘*democracy*’ and ‘*security*’ is the profit every political leader wants to gain. Also, it reveals why political leaders thrive for power as they believe ‘Nigeria’ is a business that can yield profit.

- “To members of the PDP family and members of other political parties, who have demonstrated faith in our *democratic enterprise*...” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “We must make a vow that, together, we will make the *Nigerian Enterprise thrive*.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “We shall *invest more in our security personnel*, and this means more than an increase in number ...” (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Politics is a force

In the corpus under study, there were a good number of metaphorical expressions possessing features of force. The presidents, in their speeches, conceptualised ‘*contentment*’ and *economy* as possessing natural and physical force on ‘*democracy*’, ‘*the economy*’, ‘*Nigeria*’ and her ‘*citizens*’. Examples:

- “We must ... *generate enduring happiness* for our people.” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- “We will *push programs and policies* that will benefit both local and foreign businesses...” (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- ‘First, budgetary reform *stimulating the economy* without engendering inflation will be instituted...’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Politics is a container

This conceptual metaphor considers issues in politics as though they are physical objects that can hold other items. In the expression below, “*the economy*” was viewed as “*container*” in which societal goal could be carried. Examples:

- ‘We shall instead *re-channel the funds into better investment* in public infrastructure, education, health care and jobs...’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

Politics is an entity

The formation of the idea of politics in terms of being an entity entails the concretisation of issues in politics or political activities as physical objects. In the corpus under study, the following expressions were given tangible and visible qualities: **political expectations** (sacrifice, promises, patience, trust, goodwill), **political goals** (unity, purpose, determination, hope, faith and enthusiasm), **societal challenges** (poverty, bad governance, corruption, colonialism, hopelessness and despair). Concretizing these qualities, the leaders aimed to lead the citizen to deal with these issues in politics as objects. Examples:

- “Today, *our unity is firm, our purpose is strong and our determination unshakable*”. (Goodluck Jonathan, 2011)
- ‘We are too great a nation and too grounded as a people to *rob ourselves of our finest destiny ...*’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘We *lift high this torch* so that it might shine on every household and in every heart that calls itself Nigerian ...’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘We *hold this beam aloft because it lights our path* with compassion, brotherhood, and peace ...’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘Nigeria has not held *an election of better quality...*’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘For me, *political coloration has faded away ...*’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘We must work harder at bringing these noble documents to life *by strengthening the bonds of* economic collaboration, social cohesion, and cultural understanding ...’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘Yet, we have *shouldered the heavy burden to arrive* at this SUBLIME moment where the *prospect of a better future merges with our improved capacity ...*’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)
- ‘Today, Fate and Destiny join together *to place the torch of human progress in our very hands...*’ (Bola Tinubu, 2023)

*Summary of Prevailing Metaphorical Themes in **Ontology Metaphors** Used by Goodluck Jonathan and Bola Tinubu in their Inaugural Addresses.*

Metaphorical Themes	Goodluck Jonathan (2011)	Bola Tinubu (2023)	Total
POLITICS IS A MACHINE	1	3	4
POLITICS IS FOOD	1	0	1
POLITICS IS BUSINESS	2	1	3
POLITICS IS A FORCE	2	1	3
POLITICS IS A CONTAINER	0	1	1
POLITICS IS AN ENTITY	1	8	9
	7	14	21

As it is deduced from the chart above, the most commonly used conceptual metaphor in the inaugural addresses of the post-military Nigerian presidents was the ontological metaphor. The ontological metaphor, also known as the object metaphor, expressed political issues and concepts are objects. Bola

Tinubu mostly employed the ontological metaphor compared to Goodluck Jonathan. He focused more on emphasizing the fact that political concepts and issues should be concretized and dealt with as an entity.

In the same vein, Bola Tinubu and Goodluck Jonathan generous use of war metaphor was collaborative. They both saw ‘Nigerians as ‘fighters’, ‘societal evil as enemies’ and ‘election as war’ They both saw Nigerians as ‘fighters’

Moreover, both presidents used the journey metaphor manipulatively because they wanted to paint a picture portraying the political process as a confluence of movement towards a goal. More importantly, Bola Tinubu framed Nigerians as travellers. As a result, the journey metaphor contained in the inaugural addresses of Bola Tinubu, is a quantum leap for citizens to view politics as a sort of vehicle guiding the Nigerian nation along the path to its ‘destiny’.

Figure 2. Comparison of Metaphors Used by the Two Nigerian Presidents under Study

Conclusion

This study has revealed that metaphor is pervasively used in Nigerian political discourse. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), Critical Metaphor Analysis (CMA) and Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) which are approaches to this research have enabled the researcher to reveal the post-military Nigerian presidents’ ability to create, maintain and sustain political solidarity through their usage of conceptual metaphors to manipulate their audience both

cognitively and conceptually. This study shows that the corpus is replete with metaphors of war, journey, building, time, health, human, plant, orientational, object and sport metaphors with imaging latched onto describing the following: the Nigerian nation and citizens, politicians, opponents, political activities and political challenges.

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